

Elders Learning English for Europe
2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465

**ICT TOOLS AND RESOURCES
TO SUPPORT LANGUAGE TEACHING
FOR ELDERS**

Co-funded by
the European Union

Project information

Project: Erasmus+

Project title: Elders learning English for Europe

Acronym: ELENE

Project No.: 2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465

Project coordinator: Instytut Badań i Innowacji w Edukacji, [INBIE], Poland

Project partners:

L J U D S K A
U N I V E R Z A
R O G A Ś K A
S L A T I N A

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.

Authors:

Renata OCHOA-DADERSKA - Instytut Badań i Innowacji w Edukacji – INBIE - Poland

Agnieszka CHEŃCIŃSKA-KOPIEC Kukuczka Academy of Physical Education in Katowice - Poland

Gabriela OCHOA-DADERSKA - Instytut Badań i Innowacji w Edukacji – INBIE - Poland

Kacper KOTLEWSKI - Instytut Badan i Innowacji w Edukacji – INBIE - Poland

Nataša JAKOB - Ljudska univerza Rogaška Slatina – LURS - Slovenia

Mojca VUKOVIC - Ljudska univerza Rogaška Slatina – LURS - Slovenia

Yeliz NUR AKARÇAY – Sarıçam Halk Eğitimi Merkezi Müdürlüğü - Türkiye

Alpaslan AKILLI - Sarıçam Halk Eğitimi Merkezi Müdürlüğü - Türkiye

Elisardo SANCHIS - INNETICA - Spain

Arturo José GONZÁLEZ - INNETICA - Spain

Melanie VÁZQUEZ - INNETICA - Spain

Luis OCHOA-SIGUENCIA - Kukuczka Academy of Physical Education in Katowice - Poland

Printing and binding:

Online © Fundacja Instytut Badań i Innowacji w Edukacji, Częstochowa, 2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10028141

Free publication

Programme: Erasmus+ Key Action: Partnerships for cooperation and exchange of practices; Cooperation partnerships in adult education; Project Reference: 2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465

Topics: ICT, Foreign language teaching and learning; Active ageing; Development of training courses.

More publications: Publishing INBIE: <https://publisher.inbie.pl>

Table of content

INTRODUCTION	5
THE CASE OF TÜRKIYE.....	7
THE CASE OF SLOVENIA	12
THE CASE OF SPAIN	14
THE CASE OF POLAND.....	20
SELECTION AND VALIDATION OF TOOLS AND RESOURCES	23
CONCLUSION	25
REFERENCES	26

INTRODUCTION

Learning English online can offer numerous benefits for seniors, just as it does for individuals of any age. Here are some of the advantages of seniors learning English online:

Convenience: Online learning allows seniors to study English from the comfort of their own homes. They can choose when and where they want to study, making it a flexible option that accommodates their schedules and preferences.

Self-Paced Learning: Seniors can learn at their own pace. Online courses often provide materials that can be reviewed as many times as needed, allowing seniors to take their time and grasp the language at their own speed.

Access to Resources: The internet offers a wealth of English learning resources, from language courses to grammar guides, pronunciation videos, and interactive exercises. Seniors can access a variety of free or paid resources to support their learning journey.

Improved Cognitive Health: Learning a new language is a mentally stimulating activity that can help maintain and improve cognitive functions, which is especially important for seniors.

Social Interaction: Online English courses and language learning communities provide opportunities for seniors to interact with people from around the world. This can combat social isolation and foster connections with others who share similar interests.

Travel and Cultural Understanding: English is a global language, and learning it can make traveling to English-speaking countries more enjoyable and less intimidating. It can also enhance cultural awareness and understanding of diverse cultures.

Job Opportunities: Some seniors may want to continue working or pursue part-time employment. Learning English can open up job opportunities in industries that require bilingual or English-speaking workers.

Enhanced Communication: As English is one of the most widely spoken languages globally, learning it can facilitate communication with English-speaking family members, friends, and acquaintances.

Access to Information: Much of the world's information and resources are available in English. Seniors who can read and understand English have access to a broader range of knowledge, news, and entertainment.

Mental Stimulation: Learning a new language is a complex task that involves memory, problem-solving, and linguistic analysis. This cognitive stimulation can help keep the mind sharp and active.

Personal Growth: Learning a new language is a rewarding and fulfilling experience. Seniors can gain a sense of achievement and personal growth from acquiring a new skill.

Cost-Effective: Many online resources for learning English are free or affordable. Seniors can choose from a variety of courses and materials that fit their budget.

Adaptability: Online learning platforms often offer features like subtitles, slow playback, and clear pronunciation, making it easier for seniors to adapt to the pace of the course.

In summary, learning English online can be an excellent option for seniors, offering convenience, mental stimulation, opportunities for social interaction, and personal growth. It can also open doors to new experiences, travel, and job opportunities.

The case of Türkiye

Adults, including elders, learning English for travelling purposes is a common and practical endeavour. Learning English can greatly enhance elders' travel experience, allowing them to communicate effectively, navigate unfamiliar places, and interact with locals in English-speaking and tourist attraction places in various countries.

Enhanced Communication: Knowing English helps travellers interact with people from diverse cultures, making their travel experience more immersive and enjoyable.

Increased Independence: Elder travellers gain more independence when they can understand and respond in English. This can boost their confidence while exploring new destinations.

Access to Information: English proficiency enables travellers to access information online, read signs, menus, and maps, and follow instructions in various contexts.

Cultural Understanding: Learning English can also enhance their understanding of English-speaking cultures, allowing for more meaningful interactions with locals.

On the other hand, many countries, including Türkiye, do not have well-defined and used curriculum designed for seniors learning English for travel purposes. However, some special institutions may address needs of this population in various contexts. Special courses and public education centres could be considered in this context.

Public education centres in Türkiye play a crucial role in providing lifelong learning opportunities for people of all ages, including elderly individuals. These centres offer a wide range of courses and programs tailored to the specific needs and interests of older learners as well. Public education centres support lifelong learning for elderly individuals as follows:

- 1. Diverse Course Offerings:** Public education centres provide diverse courses, including language classes, computer literacy programs, art and craft workshops, dance and music lessons, health and wellness seminars, and more. These offerings cater to various interests, allowing elderly learners to explore new skills and hobbies.

2. **Social Interaction:** Lifelong learning programs in public education centres create social spaces where elderly individuals can interact with peers who share similar interests. This social interaction fosters a sense of community and combats social isolation, which is common among seniors.
3. **Cognitive Stimulation:** Engaging in lifelong learning activities stimulates the brain, promoting cognitive health and preventing cognitive decline. Activities like learning a new language, solving puzzles, or taking up creative arts enhance mental agility and memory.
4. **Health and Wellness Programs:** Many public education centres offer health and wellness workshops, including nutrition classes and stress management sessions. These programs promote physical and mental well-being, encouraging a healthier lifestyle among elderly learners.
5. **Flexibility and Accessibility:** Lifelong learning programs are often designed with flexible schedules to accommodate the needs of elderly individuals. Classes may be offered during non-working hours, allowing retirees to participate. Additionally, some centres provide online courses, making learning accessible to those who prefer remote learning.
6. **Personal Growth:** Lifelong learning empowers elderly individuals by boosting their self-esteem and confidence. Acquiring new skills and knowledge instils a sense of achievement, contributing to personal growth and a positive outlook on life. Learning a new language can increase all these positive effects.
7. **Intergenerational Learning:** Public education centres sometimes facilitate intergenerational learning experiences, where older adults share their wisdom and experiences with younger learners, fostering mutual understanding and respect between generations.
8. **Affordable Education:** Lifelong learning programs at public education centres are often affordable or even free, ensuring that financial constraints do not hinder access to education for elderly individuals. To summarize, public education centres serve as invaluable hubs for lifelong learning, providing elderly individuals with opportunities to socialize, learn new skills, stay mentally and physically active, and enrich their lives well into their golden age.

In the realm of language teaching for older adults, limited research exists on curriculum development, textbook publication, and specific teaching methodologies tailored to this demographic in Turkey. The picture is not very different in many other countries. However, some international publications provide valuable suggestions for language instructors. Persidsky and Kelly (1992) recommended bilingual teachers for Russian adults learning English in the US. Weinstein-Shr (1993) emphasized the need for a favourable learning environment for older learners, considering their potential vision problems, and advocated for educational materials in large-print formats. Grognet (1997) stressed the importance of adapting the curriculum to older adult learners' specific needs and preferences, highlighting the role of engaging and relevant content. Grasso (2016) addressed language anxiety among older learners, emphasizing the significance of a comfortable learning environment, authentic materials, and learner-oriented teaching approaches. Ramirez Gomez (2016) underscored the challenges posed by ageist attitudes and advocated for a content-based approach, critiquing the suitability of the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) for older learners.

Apart from instructional challenges, administrative issues also affect language education for older adults. Studies highlighted the lack of available language courses, often resulting in limited class frequency and level options, potentially due to funding constraints or misconceptions about older learners' abilities (Hubenthal, 2004). To address these challenges, teachers must tailor their teaching methods to meet the specific needs of older learners, fostering engaging conversations and creating well-lit, quiet classrooms. Additionally, course materials should be age-appropriate, and the CEFR criteria should be adjusted to better suit older adults. Institutions must expand their offerings, providing a variety of class levels during evening sessions to accommodate older learners effectively. These recommendations can be taken into consideration while designing any learning program for older adults in Türkiye.

These recommendations can be summarized as follows:

- **Bilingual Instructors:** Consider employing bilingual instructors for language classes targeting older adults, enhancing the learning experience.
- **Conducive Learning Environment:** Provide a well-lit, quiet, and comfortable environment for older learners, accommodating potential vision problems and ensuring a positive atmosphere.

- **Large-Print Materials:** Develop educational materials in large-print formats to aid older learners with potential visual impairments, promoting accessibility.
- **Flexible Teaching Approaches:** Be flexible in teaching methods, acknowledging the diverse learning strategies older adults may have developed over time, ensuring a personalized and adaptable learning experience.
- **Engaging Content:** Design course content that is engaging and relevant to older learners, avoiding mundane or irrelevant material. Focus on topics and activities that captivate their interest.
- **Address Language Anxiety:** Address language anxiety among older learners by creating a comfortable learning environment, utilizing authentic materials, and adopting learner-oriented teaching styles.
- **Content-Based Approach:** Implement a content-based teaching approach, emphasizing meaningful content over rigid language rules, catering to the specific learning needs of older adults.
- **Age-Appropriate Material:** Ensure course materials are age-appropriate, aligning with the interests and experiences of older learners, making the learning process more relatable and engaging.
- **Reassess CEFR Criteria:** Consider revising the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) to better suit the unique learning styles and needs of older adults, allowing for a more tailored language education experience.
- **Expand Course Offerings:** Institutions should expand their language course offerings, providing classes at various levels during evening sessions to accommodate the diverse proficiency levels of older learners effectively.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) have become indispensable across society, catering to various age groups. ICT tools like computers, the internet, and mobile phones are now considered essential for daily activities. Overall, ICT plays a pivotal role in enhancing communication, accessing services, and improving the overall well-being of elderly individuals.

In Türkiye, the elderly population has been steadily increasing, constituting 8.3% of the total population in 2017, up from 7.5% in 2012. Despite the country's efforts in digitalizing government and private services, the specific needs and expectations of the elderly regarding information and communication technologies (ICT) are often overlooked in the

design of digital products and services. Both public and private sectors have been transitioning to digital platforms, including the e-Government Gateway. However, there is a lack of mature research in the field of human-computer interaction (HCI) concerning the use of ICT by senior citizens in Türkiye.

This indicates a gap in understanding and addressing the unique requirements of the elderly population in the digital landscape. Projects targeting this age group are believed to address this gap.

The case of Slovenia

In Slovenia, different organizations offer English courses to seniors:

- Language Schools: Many language schools in Slovenia offer English courses tailored for senior citizens
- Adult Education Centres: Adult education centres often provide language courses for adults of all ages
- Community Centres: Community centres and senior centres may organize English language classes; they are often accessible and provide a comfortable learning environment
- Retirement Communities: In some retirement communities, they offer language courses as part of their activities
- Local Universities and Colleges: Some universities and colleges offer lifelong learning or continuing education programs that include English language courses for older adults.

Although the offer of English courses in Slovenia is very big, our research has shown that online English courses for seniors are almost non-existent in Slovenia. During the Covid-19 situation there were some attempts to set up some individual online English courses from seniors, but nothing was made on a national basis so each organization that works with seniors was left on its own to try to manage some kind of online version of language learning.

An example of good practice comes from organization Porečje Sore that offers English online courses from seniors. Their theory is that many do not have time for a classical language course, but they are still good speakers. They can choose e-learning of a foreign language at their own pace, anywhere and anytime. They learn the language independently or in combination with conversations with the teacher. If they want, they change the level of knowledge, and sometimes even change the language of the course. More and more of them are choosing a 100% mobile solution.

Depending on their needs, learning habits and set goals, seniors can choose between two forms of e-learning:

- Self-Study which enables independent e-learning anywhere and anytime without the help of a tutor
- Studying with a coach which is an ideal combination of e-learning and a course with a teacher which is proven to be the most successful method of learning.
- Seniors can choose between:
 - E-course for beginners - (Foundations) adapted to pure beginners or to those who would like to repeat the basics
 - Continuing e-course - (Fluency Builder) which is an ideal choice for those who already have good knowledge of a foreign language.

The organization offers this option because they believe that e-learning is the most flexible solution and an ideal solution that enables language learning even when, due to numerous obligations and unpredictable schedules, seniors cannot go to the course at the predetermined time. This way of learning enables 24/7 study when it suits you: morning,

evening, night... At the same time, seniors can set their own learning pace, start learning at any time, spend an unlimited number of hours in the program (via mobile app or browser) and choose the contents themselves and design their own customized program.

The organization offers seniors a 100% mobile e-course. They can access all content and tests and set goals via the mobile application. They can also track their progress in the web and mobile app and access the content even when the internet connection is not available (applies to the advanced course).

But as mentioned, this organization is more of an exception to a rule. We could claim that the low level of offer of online English courses comes from the fact that ICT skills of seniors in Slovenia are still on a quite low level and for seniors learning and improving ICT skills is a big enough challenge on its own, therefore they could consider adding online English learning too difficult and too stressful for them. It is expected that it will be easier for future generations, where ICT skills will be more developed, to choose an online option for learning English, but this is more the case for the future, at least in Slovenia.

The case of Spain

The context of language learning among the elderly in Spain is shaped by several critical factors that highlight the significance of this study. Spain, like many other developed countries, is experiencing a demographic shift characterized by a growing elderly population.

Life expectancy has steadily increased, and birth rates have declined, leading to an increasingly aged demographic. This demographic transformation presents both challenges and opportunities for various facets of society, including education. As Spain's population ages, there is a growing need to address the unique educational needs and aspirations of the elderly. Traditional education systems, primarily designed for younger generations, may not adequately cater to the learning preferences and requirements of elderly learners.

In this context, language learning emerges as a particularly relevant area of focus. Language acquisition offers numerous benefits for the elderly, extending far beyond the development of language skills. For this demographic, learning languages can serve as a powerful tool for cognitive stimulation and mental health maintenance. Research indicates that engaging in language learning exercises memory, problem-solving abilities, and critical thinking skills, thereby contributing to the preservation of cognitive function in old age.

Furthermore, language learning promotes social inclusion and interaction among the elderly.

Loneliness and social isolation are common challenges faced by older individuals, and language classes or language exchange groups provide opportunities for meaningful social connections. Engaging in language learning can foster a sense of belonging, reduce feelings of isolation, and enhance overall emotional well-being.

Effective communication is another crucial aspect of the elderly's quality of life. Proficiency in multiple languages allows elderly individuals to express themselves more clearly and comprehensively. This improved communication reduces frustration in interpersonal relationships and facilitates meaningful connections with family members, friends, and caregivers. Enhanced communication leads to better emotional and psychological well-being, promoting a sense of empowerment and autonomy among elderly learners.

Furthermore, learning a language provides a portal to cultural enrichment, which is especially important in the context of Spain due to its linguistic diversity. With multiple official languages and regional dialects, Spain boasts a rich tapestry of cultures. Learning different languages allows elderly individuals to explore and appreciate various cultures, fostering curiosity, open-mindedness, and a deeper connection to their own heritage. This cultural enrichment adds to the richness and fulfillment of life for elderly learners.

Moreover, language learning aligns with the concept of lifelong learning and personal growth, which resonates strongly with many elderly individuals. It provides them with an avenue to continue setting and achieving new goals, pursuing intellectual interests, and embracing new challenges even after retirement. This ongoing journey of learning

enhances their sense of purpose and accomplishment, ultimately promoting mental and emotional well-being.

In conclusion, understanding the background and significance of language learning for the elderly in Spain underscores the need to address their unique needs and preferences in education. The multifaceted benefits of language learning emphasize the importance of integrating ICT tools and resources to support their language education effectively.

Benefits of ICT in Elderly Language Learning

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into elderly language learning in Spain offers a range of valuable benefits. These benefits are particularly crucial for older individuals seeking to acquire or enhance their language skills. Let's explore these benefits in detail:

Flexibility and Convenience:

ICT tools and resources provide elderly language learners with unmatched flexibility and convenience:

- **Self-Paced Learning:** Many online language learning platforms and apps allow elderly learners to progress at their own pace. This flexibility is particularly important as it accommodates varying learning speeds and schedules. Elderly learners can choose when and for how long they wish to study, making it easier to incorporate language learning into their daily routines.
- **Accessibility:** ICT tools are accessible from anywhere with an internet connection. This accessibility eliminates the need for elderly learners to travel to physical classrooms, especially relevant for those with mobility issues. Language learning can take place from the comfort of their homes, which is often preferred by older individuals.
- **24/7 Availability:** Online resources and language learning apps are available 24/7. This means elderly learners can engage with language learning at any time that suits them, whether it is during the day, in the evening, or even late at night. Such flexibility is vital for accommodating different lifestyles and preferences.

Engagement and Interactivity:

ICT tools and resources enhance engagement and interactivity in the language learning process:

- **Gamification:** Many language learning apps incorporate gamification elements, turning language learning into an interactive and enjoyable experience. Older learners can complete quizzes, earn points, and track their progress, making the process more engaging and motivating.
- **Interactive Exercises:** Online platforms and apps provide a wide range of interactive exercises, such as listening comprehension, pronunciation practice, and vocabulary drills. These exercises are not only beneficial for language skill development but also keep elderly learners actively engaged in the learning process.

- **Immediate Feedback:** ICT resources often offer immediate feedback on exercises and quizzes. This real-time feedback is valuable for older individuals as it allows them to correct their mistakes and learn from them, promoting a sense of accomplishment and progress.

Cognitive Benefits:

Engaging with ICT tools in language learning can lead to significant cognitive benefits for elderly individuals:

- **Mental Stimulation:** Language learning itself is a mentally stimulating activity. It challenges the brain to acquire new vocabulary, grammar rules, and pronunciation skills. This cognitive exercise can help maintain and improve cognitive function, particularly memory and problem-solving abilities.
- **Lifelong Learning:** Engaging in language learning through ICT tools promotes the concept of lifelong learning. This continuous engagement in intellectual pursuits can delay cognitive decline and contribute to healthy aging.
- **Social Interaction:** Many ICT tools also enable social interaction through online language exchange and discussion forums. Social engagement has been linked to cognitive well-being, helping elderly learners stay mentally active.

In conclusion, the integration of ICT tools and resources into elderly language learning in Spain brings about essential benefits. These benefits include flexibility and convenience, enhanced engagement and interactivity, and significant cognitive advantages. They cater to the diverse needs and preferences of older learners, making language learning more accessible, engaging, and supportive for elderly individuals in their language learning journeys.

ICT Tools and Resources for Elderly Language Learners

When it comes to supporting language learning for the elderly in Spain, various ICT tools and resources can be valuable. These tools are designed to cater to the unique needs and preferences of elderly learners, providing flexibility, accessibility, and interactivity. Here is a detailed breakdown of the key ICT tools and resources:

Online Language Learning Platforms:

Online language learning platforms are web-based tools and websites that provide structured courses for learning languages. They are designed to cater to a wide range of languages and are user-friendly to accommodate elderly learners who may not be tech-savvy. These platforms offer a variety of interactive lessons, exercises, and quizzes to engage users. They often allow learners to set their own pace, making them ideal for self-directed study. Features such as pronunciation guides and speech recognition can help users practice language production. Online language learning platforms also frequently include cultural insights, fostering a deeper understanding of the language being learned.

Language Learning Mobile Applications:

Language learning mobile applications are smartphone and tablet apps designed for language education. They offer several advantages, such as accessibility and flexibility. Elderly learners can access these apps on their own devices, making it convenient for them to engage in language learning on the go. The lessons in these apps are often divided into manageable sections, allowing users to study in short, focused sessions. Many language learning apps incorporate gamified elements, progress tracking, and immediate feedback to motivate and engage learners. This feature can be particularly appealing to elderly learners looking for interactive and goal-oriented language learning experiences.

Free Online Language Resources:

Free online language resources encompass websites, blogs, and YouTube channels that offer a wide range of information for language learners. These resources can be particularly useful for elderly individuals who are on a budget. They typically provide access to grammar explanations, vocabulary lists, cultural insights, and language-related content without any cost. While these resources may lack the structured approach of paid language learning platforms, they are excellent for supplementary learning, self-study, and exploration of specific language topics of interest. This flexibility allows elderly learners to access information at their own pace and according to their individual interests.

Videoconferencing and Online Classes:

Videoconferencing tools and online classes provide the elderly with opportunities for real-time, interactive language learning. Videoconferencing platforms like Zoom, Skype, or Microsoft Teams enable live communication with instructors and fellow learners. This live interaction creates a sense of community and combats social isolation, which is particularly important for elderly learners. Online language classes often offer structured lesson plans, allowing learners to ask questions, engage in group discussions, and receive immediate feedback from instructors. These classes can provide a more structured learning environment for elderly individuals who prefer guidance and regular interaction.

Customization and Accessibility Features:

Customization and accessibility features in ICT tools and resources are crucial for accommodating the unique needs of elderly learners. Many platforms allow users to customize their learning experience by adjusting font sizes, changing color themes for better readability, or enabling text-to-speech functionality. These features are especially beneficial for learners with visual impairments or limited mobility, as they enhance the usability of the tools. Customizable interfaces and content empower elderly learners to tailor their language learning journey to their preferences and needs. This personalization fosters greater engagement and user satisfaction, making language learning more enjoyable and effective.

In summary, these ICT tools and resources cater to the needs of elderly language learners in Spain by offering accessibility, interactivity, customization, and a variety of options. These tools not only facilitate language acquisition but also address the challenges faced by elderly learners, making language learning more engaging and effective. Their flexibility allows elderly individuals to embark on language learning journeys that align with their abilities and interests.

Case Studies

Examining case studies that showcase the successful implementation of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) in elderly language learning offers valuable insights into practical approaches and outcomes. These case studies, specifically those from Spain, shed light on how various institutions and initiatives have harnessed ICT tools and resources to support language education among the elderly.

Successful Implementation of ICT in Elderly Language Learning:

Case studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of integrating ICT tools and resources into language education for elderly individuals. Some notable examples include:

1. **Virtual Language Classes:** Several language schools and community organizations in Spain have successfully transitioned to virtual language classes using videoconferencing tools like Zoom or Microsoft Teams. These platforms have enabled elderly learners to participate in live language classes, interact with instructors and peers, and engage in real-time conversations, all from the safety and comfort of their homes.
2. **Online Language Learning Platforms:** Organizations have integrated online language learning platforms that offer structured courses for elderly learners. These platforms incorporate user-friendly interfaces, interactive lessons, and self-paced learning options. Elderly individuals can access these resources at their convenience, helping them engage with language learning in a flexible manner.
3. **Tailored Content:** Some case studies have highlighted the importance of tailoring language learning content to the specific needs and interests of elderly learners. This includes creating resources that focus on practical language skills needed for daily communication, such as shopping, healthcare, and social interactions.
4. **Digital Literacy Training:** In certain cases, successful implementation has involved providing elderly learners with digital literacy training alongside language education. This approach ensures that they are not only proficient in the target language but also in the use of the necessary digital tools and resources.

Real-Life Examples from Spain:

Real-life examples from Spain illustrate how local institutions, language schools, and community centers have embraced ICT to facilitate language learning among the elderly:

1. Duolingo: Duolingo offers courses in numerous languages, making it a versatile choice for seniors across Europe looking to learn languages like English, French, German, and more. Its user-friendly interface and gamified approach make it accessible.
2. Babbel: Babbel provides language courses in various European and world languages. Seniors in Europe can use it to learn languages like English, French, Italian, and many others, with a focus on practical communication.
3. Rosetta Stone: Rosetta Stone offers comprehensive language learning courses for multiple languages. It uses an immersive method to teach pronunciation and conversational skills, which can be valuable for older learners.
4. BBC Languages: The BBC Languages website offers free language courses in languages other than English. Seniors across Europe can explore courses in French, German, Spanish, and more, complete with interactive exercises and multimedia resources.
5. Tandem: Tandem is a platform for seniors in Europe to practice conversational skills in various languages. It connects users with native speakers for language exchange, facilitating cultural and linguistic interactions.
6. Online Language Exchange Groups: Platforms like Meetup and conversationexchange.com are used by language enthusiasts and seniors across Europe to find language exchange groups and partners for practicing different languages.
7. Language Learning Apps: Popular language learning apps like Memrise, FluentU, and Drops offer courses in multiple languages. Seniors in Europe can explore these apps to study various languages, including European languages like German, Dutch, and Portuguese.
8. Local Language Classes: Many European community centers and language schools offer language classes for seniors in languages such as English, French, or German. These classes may also incorporate digital resources for language learning.
9. Community Language Clubs: Seniors can join local language clubs or online forums focused on specific languages, providing opportunities for language practice and cultural exchange across Europe.
10. YouTube Language Learning Channels: YouTube hosts various language learning channels catering to different languages. For example, 'Easy Languages' offers video lessons for various European languages, making it accessible and engaging for older learners.

These examples offer specific tools and resources that elderly individuals in Europe, and specially in Spain, can use to learn languages other than their native language. Whether they are interested in European languages or languages from other parts of the world, these digital resources facilitate lifelong language learning and cultural exploration.

The case of Poland

In today's world, the ability to speak English is becoming increasingly important not only for young people but also for seniors. It allows them to communicate with other people, access global knowledge and culture, and keep their minds active. For seniors, there are many online English learning tools available, both free and paid, to help achieve this goal.

There are a number of online English language learning tools available for both beginners and advanced learners. Here are some popular Polish online English learning tools:

- eTutor.co.uk: eTutor is a popular educational platform offering online English courses. It provides a variety of interactive lessons, exercises, and tests to help you learn English at different levels.
- English Online: is a website offering free lessons and resources for learning English.
It has a variety of exercises, audio recordings, and articles.
- Duolingo Polish: The popular mobile app Duolingo is also available in a Polish-language version. It offers English lessons in the form of games and fun.
- LinguaLeo: is an online English language learning platform with access in Polish. It features interactive lessons, dictionaries, and the ability to learn by reading texts.
- English in a Pill: The Blog and website offer free English lessons, audiovisual material, and educational articles.
- BBC English Learning (Polish version): offers educational material in Polish, making it easy to access valuable English learning resources.
- Busuu: is a social language learning platform that provides courses in multiple languages, including English, with access to Polish.
- Rosetta Stone (Polish version): Rosetta Stone offers paid English courses, but versions of the interface in Polish are also available.
- English in Emigration: The website provides useful educational material and guidance for English learners in an expat context.
- English Club Poland: This is the Polish version of the English Club website, which offers free lessons, exercises, and tools for learning English.

The choice of English language learning tools depends on individual preferences and needs. Some of these platforms offer free resources, while others require fees to access advanced features. It is also advised to practice the language on a regular basis and use a variety of resources to increase the effectiveness of your learning.

Here are five good and up-to-date free online English learning sites that offer a variety of materials tailored to contemporary events:

- BBC Learning English: It is a reputable website offering educational material in English. Seniors can find videos, texts, and podcasts that are tailored to different levels of expertise. The site includes sections on grammar, business English and interactive language games and activities.
- Learning English / Cambridge English: The site offers a rich collection of various online exercises to learn English at different levels, from A1 to C2. The exercises address different language skills such as listening, reading, writing and speaking.

- VOA Learning English: VOA Learning English is a source of articles and videos focused on learning American English. The materials are available at three different levels: basic, intermediate, and advanced.
- TED Talks: Although it is not a website solely dedicated to learning English, the TED Talks platform offers thousands of inspiring speeches on a variety of topics. Valuable for advanced learners, speeches can be viewed with or without subtitles.
- Anglophenia (YouTube channel): Anglophenia is a YouTube channel that explores the English language and British and American culture. Seniors can find dozens of recordings on English language and cultural trivia.

These websites and platforms offer a variety of materials that can help seniors to learn English online, regardless of their level. These platforms also allow tailoring learning to their own preferences and topics of interest.

Free online tools for learning English:

Advantages:

- Free availability: Free tools are available to everyone, a huge plus for seniors with limited financial resources.
- Wide access to materials: Many free platforms offer a range of lessons, exercises and learning materials, giving seniors plenty of opportunities to learn.
- Self-reliance: Seniors can learn at their own pace and on their own schedule without being constrained by deadlines or costs.

Disadvantages:

- Lack of personalized support: Lack of interaction with the teacher can make it difficult for seniors to solve problems or get answers to questions.
- Less motivation: Lack of financial commitments can make some seniors treat learning more superficially and lose motivation.
- Lack of official certificates: Without paying for courses, seniors may not obtain official certificates to prove their skills, which may be needed in some situations.

Paid online tools for learning English:

Advantages:

- Access to professional teachers: Paid tools often offer the opportunity to learn with experienced teachers, which provides personalized help and support.
- Structure and timetable: Paid platforms often offer a clear learning program, which helps seniors to maintain regularity and progress.
- Certificates and accreditations: Paid courses often award official certificates that can be useful in the labour market or in the emigration process.

Disadvantages:

- Costs: Paid tools require payment, which can be a financial burden, especially for seniors on a fixed pension or disability income.
- Less time flexibility: Seniors may have to adjust to course schedules, which can be difficult with permanent classes or other commitments.
- Dependence on the Internet and technology: Paid tools require Internet access and computer skills, which can be problematic for some seniors.

In conclusion, both free and paid online English language learning tools have their advantages and disadvantages. The choice depends on preferences, financial availability, and the individual needs of seniors. It is important to choose the tool that best suits personal learning goals and abilities.

Selection and validation of tools and resources

Elene consortium has tested several English language tools and resources available on the Internet. These tools and resources served as a base for developing tools and resources for the Elders learning English for Europe ERASMUS+ nr. 2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465 project [ELENE project] Coordinated by Instytut Badań I Innowacji w Edukacji [Poland] in collaboration with Asociacion de innovacion emprendimiento y tecnologias de la informacion y la comunicacion [Spain]; Glandrive, unipessoal lda [Portugal]; Ljudska univerza, zavod za izobrazevanje in kulturo, rogaska slatina [Slovenia] and Saricam Halk Egitimi Merkezi [Türkiye].

The different tools were analysed, taking into account the objective of the project and target group needs:

- To improve and expand the offer of high-quality learning opportunities adapted to the needs of older people to improve their multilingual skills (English language learning) and digital skills.
- To expand and develop the skills of trainers and other staff that support older people, especially to motivate them to participate in foreign language learning and effective teaching.

The target group can be summarized:

- Teachers/staff who support the teaching of foreign languages to the elderly.
- Elderly people with an interest in learning languages and having a low level of knowledge of English.

The most popular tools and resources can be divided into two groups:

a. Free online English language learning tools for seniors:

Duolingo: Duolingo is a popular educational platform that offers language courses in the form of games and fun. It is user-friendly for all ages and offers free access to basic English courses.

BBC Learning English: BBC Learning English website offers numerous educational resources such as videos, articles, and exercises to help you learn English. It is an excellent source of information and practice for seniors.

YouTube: Videos on the YouTube platform can be an excellent source of learning. There are many channels that offer English lessons for seniors, both in the form of lessons and educational material.

Memrise: Memrise is a platform based on learning through repetition. It offers language courses in a variety of areas that can be adapted to the needs of seniors.

b. Paid online English language learning tools for seniors:

Rosetta Stone: Rosetta Stone is a well-known learning platform that offers English courses in the form of interactive lessons. Although it is paid, it provides advanced learning tools.

Babbel: Babbel is a platform that focuses on practical language skills. It offers lessons tailored to different levels and is available for a fee.

italki: italki is an online language learning platform that allows seniors to learn with real teachers. It is a paid option but guarantees interactive learning.

Cambridge English Online: Cambridge University Press offers fee-based online courses for seniors that prepare them for English examinations. These are more advanced courses, ideal for those who want to gain a certificate.

It is worth noting that the choice between free and paid tools depends on seniors' individual preferences and financial capabilities.

Conclusion

The tools and resources developed by the ELENE consortium are innovative and are the effect of several months of testing and research. We decided to develop:

- [Webpage](#) of the project
- A friendly [e-learning platform](#) for elderly people learning English as a foreign language
- Study material ([textbook](#)) for learners (Elders)
- Methodology [manual for trainers](#)
- Downloadable short videos which are available on the [ELENE YouTube channel](#)
- [Elene App](#) which is available in Google Play Store

The e-learning platform serves as a means of support for learning the language and checking older people to verify what they do in regular (face-to-face) classes. Therefore, it complements their non-formal education activities.

All tools can be used online and offline, free available, and downloadable.

The textbooks have been divided into units that can be downloaded to laptops and computers to be able to use the full interactive PDF versions.

The units to be developed in the interactive PDFs were discussed in small groups using brainstorm techniques. The topics focused on everyday situations that elderly people have to deal with. The main objective of the chosen topics is to develop the communication skills of the elders (without depending too much on grammar). It covers situations such as introducing oneself, in a café, shopping, asking for directions, at the airport/station, at the doctor, in a hotel, at a bank, my hobbies and free time and so on.

The e-learning platform includes pictures and links to videos developed by the coordinator and uploaded to the ELENE YouTube Channel.

The App developed by INBIE experts is available on Google Play Store. In addition to the sample situations, the App includes phrases, vocabulary, and some more common English language practice exercises.

References

Grasso, G. M. (2016). Language anxiety: A study of communication apprehension and willingness to communicate in the older adult EFL learners' context (Unpublished Master's dissertation. Universita Ca' Foscari Venezia), Venice, Italy.

Grognet, A. G. (1997). *Elderly refugees and language learning. US department of education report*. Washington, USA: Center for Applied Linguistics.

Hubenthal, W. (2004). Older Russian immigrants' experiences in learning English: Motivation, methods, and barriers. *Adult Basic Education*, 14(2), 104–126.

İşpınar Akçayoğlu, Duygu & Akarcay, Yeliz & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Ochoa-Daderska, Renata. (2022). Elders learning English for Europe: The Turkish case. 10.5281/zenodo.6651774.

JAKOB, Nataša & Ochoa-Daderska, Renata & VUKOVIC, Mojca & Akarcay, Yeliz & Ochoa-Daderska, Gabriela & Kopiec, Agnieszka & AKILLI, Alpaslan & ANLAR, Emine & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2023). CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING: Elders Learning English for Europe. 10.5281/zenodo.7918282.

Kuklewicz, A., & King, J. (2018). It's never too late: A narrative inquiry of older polish adults' english language learning experiences. *The Electronic Journal for English as a Second Language*, 22(3), 1–22.

Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Gómez-Ullate, Martin & Herman, Damian. (2015). Use of online collaborative writing tools by learners of higher education.

Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Herman, Damian & Marzano, Gilberto. (2015). Creating effective online collaborative learning groups at higher education institutions.

Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Kopiec, Agnieszka. (2019). Crowdsourcing solutions for supporting collaborative learning: a case of undergraduate management learners. 10.21125/edulearn.2019.1489.

Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Marzano, Gilberto & Kaczmarczyk, Patrycja. (2017). Online work-space-shared management to support collaborative learning.

Ochoa-Daderska, Renata & Kopiec, Agnieszka & Ochoa-Daderska, Gabriela & Kotlewski, Kacper & Akarcay, Yeliz & Sousa, Pedro & Akilli, Alpaslan & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2022). Elders learning English for Europe: The Portuguese case. 10.5281/zenodo.7192464.

Ochoa-Daderska, Renata & Ochoa-Daderska, Gabriela & Sánchez-García, Javier & Callarisa Fiol, Luis & Navikiene, Zivile & Navikaite, Justina & Demirci, Metin & Kopiec, Agnieszka & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2023). Exploring Digital Tools for Adult Education Trainers: Best Practices Across Europe. 10.5281/zenodo.8395367.

Ochoa-Daderska, Renata & Ochoa-Daderska, Gabriela & Sánchez-García, Javier & Callarisa Fiol, Luis & Navikiene, Zivile & Navikaite, Justina & Demerci, Metin & Gródek-Szostak, Zofia & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2023). Digital competence map for adult education facilitators. 10.5281/zenodo.8395035.

Ochoa-Daderska, Renata & Ochoa-Daderska, Gabriela & Sánchez-García, Javier & Callarisa Fiol, Luis & Navikiene, Zivile & Navikaite, Justina & Demirci, Metin & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2023). Digital Landscape: Perspectives of Trainers and Learners on Adult Digital Social Inclusion. 10.5281/zenodo.8395477.

Ochoa-Daderska, Renata & Ochoa-Daderska, Gabriela & Sánchez-García, Javier & Callarisa Fiol, Luis & Navikiene, Zivile & Navikaite, Justina & Demirci, Metin & Gródek-Szostak, Zofia & Kopiec, Agnieszka & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2023). Social inclusion through digital learning and volunteering: DigIN report II. 10.5281/zenodo.8268086.

Ochoa-Daderska, Renata & Ochoa-Daderska, Gabriela & Sánchez-García, Javier & Callarisa Fiol, Luis & Navikiene, Zivile & Navikaite, Justina & Demirci, Metin & Gródek-Szostak, Zofia & Niemczyk, Agata & Szelaġ-Sikora, Anna & Kopiec, Agnieszka & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2023). Professional use of ICT -based solutions for social Integration: DigIN report I. 10.5281/zenodo.7662148.

Origin Learning. (2015). *4 Ways to Apply Situated Learning Theory*. Available on the 15th June 2022 through: <https://blog.originlearning.com/4-ways-to-apply-the-situated-learning-theory/>

Pappas, C. (2015, 19th September). *The Impact Of Situated Cognition In eLearning*. Available on 17th June 2022 through: <https://elearningindustry.com/impact-of-situated-cognition-in-elearning/amp>

Persidsky, I. V., & Kelly, J. J. (1992). Adjustment of soviet elderly in the United States: An educational approach. In C. Berdes, A. A. Zych, & G. D. Dawson (Eds.), *Gerogogics: European research in gerontological education and educational gerontology* (pp. 129–140). Binghamton, NY: Hawort Press.

Pižorn K., PEVEC SEMEC K. (2010) Izhodišča za uvajanje dodatnih jezikov v 1. VIO. V: Lipavic Oštir, Alja (ur.), Jazbec, Saša (ur.). Pot v večjezičnost - zgodnje učenje tujih jezikov v 1. VIO osnovne šole. Ljubljana: Zavod RS za šolstvo, 106 – 168. <http://www.zrss.si/pdf/vecjezicnost.pdf>.

Prince, M. (2004). Does active learning work? A review of the research. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 93(3), 223- 231.

Rambusch, J. (2004). *Embodiment and situated learning*. Skovde: School of Humanities and Informatics. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:3324/FULLTEXT02.pdf>

Ramirez Gomez, D. (2016). Critical geragogy and foreign language learning: An exploratory application. *Educational Gerontology*, [42\(2\)](#), 136–143. doi:10.1080/03601277.2015.1083388

VUKOVIC, Mojca & Ochoa-Daderska, Renata & Akarcay, Yeliz & Gródek-Szostak, Zofia & Niemczyk, Agata & AKILLI, Alpaslan & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2022). SITUATED LEARNING METHODOLOGY: Elders learning English for Europe. 10.5281/zenodo.6878059.

Weinstein-Shr, G. (1993). Growing old in America: Learning English literacy in the later years. *ERIC Digest*.